

Plot of all 60 eigenvalues of normal equations NEQ03 (1983 March 16); no constraints. One would expect rank = 57 (i.e. 3 smallest eigenvalues $\sim 10^{-6}$ of the largest) due to the undefined coordinate system (the solution neglects proper motions). However, the condition number is only about 250, although there is indeed a jump of almost 1 dex to the last three eigenvalues. This jump increases with decreasing FOV width (here 10^0), indicating that the non-singularity has to do with the finite ordinates. It must be the postulated RGC poles which define the coordinate system.